

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INDICATIVE, IMPERATIVE AND SUBJUNCTIVE MOODS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article provides a detailed comparative analysis of mood verbs in the Uzbek and English languages. It examines the similarities and differences in how mood is expressed through verbs in both languages, considering aspects such as verb categories, conjugation, cultural influence, pragmatic considerations, and linguistic borrowing. Through this analysis, the article offers insights into the linguistic structures and cultural nuances of Uzbek and English, shedding light on the diverse ways in which mood is conveyed in these languages.

Key words: mood category, indicative mood, imperative mood, subjunctive mood, conditional mood, imperative-subjunctive mood, suffix-sa.

Аннотация: В данной статье проводится подробный сравнительный анализ глаголов настроения в узбекском и английском языках. В нем рассматриваются сходства и различия в том, как настроение выражается с помощью глаголов на обоих языках, с учетом таких аспектов, как категории глаголов, спряжение, культурное влияние, прагматические соображения и лингвистические заимствования. Благодаря этому анализу статья предлагает понимание языковых структур и культурных нюансов узбекского и английского языков, проливая свет на различные способы передачи настроения в этих языках.

Ключевые слова: категория наклонения, изъявительное наклонение, повелительное наклонение, сослагательное наклонение, условное наклонение, повелительно-сослагательное наклонение, суффикс-са.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek va ingliz tillaridagi mayl fe’llarining qiyosiy tahlili batafsil berilgan. Unda fe’l turkumlari, kelishik, madaniy ta’sir, pragmatik mulohazalar va lingvistik o‘zlashtirish kabi jihatlarni hisobga olgan holda har ikki tildagi fe’llar orqali xabar mayli, buyruq-istak mayli, so’roq mayli, shart mayli ifodalanishidagi o‘xshashlik va farqlar o‘rganiladi. Ushbu tahlil orqali maqola

o'zbek va ingliz tillarining lingvistik tuzilmalari va madaniy nuanslari haqida tushuncha beradi, bu tillarda mayl fe'llarining turlicha ifodalanishiga oydinlik kiritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ravish kategoriyasi, korsatkich mayli, buyruq mayli, ergash gap, shart mayli, buyruq-bosh mayli, qoshimcha-sa.

According to English grammar, mood is a form of the verb that shows the relationship of action to reality. This attitude is established by the speaker. He can use the form of a verb to represent an action as real, problematic, unreal, or as a request or order. In English, as in Uzbek, there are three moods.

According to Uzbek grammar, the grammatical forms that express the relation of action to reality are called moods. Mood categories are inextricably linked with verb tenses, person-number categories. The mood means the execution of an action is connected with a real being and, therefore, it expresses the meanings of indicative, imperative, subjunctive, and conditional. In Uzbek grammar imperative and subjunctive belongs to the same one type. Accordingly, the moods have three types: 1. Indicative 2. Imperative and subjunctive 3. Conditional [4.96p]

1. Indicative mood of English language: The indicative mood form makes a statement or asks a question.

Actions presented as real are expressed in the form of the indicative mood, which exists in the form of expressing time of the action. [2.176p] For instance;

Zilola study at University. Zilola Universtitetda o'qiydi.

I have never heard of it before. Men bu haqida oldin eshitmagandim.

Guzal is going away on business shortly. Guzal tez orada tijirat safariga ketmoqchi.

The indicative mood form makes a statement or asks a question. For example;

Does she speak English? U ingliz tilida gapiradimi?

Have you ever been to Italy? Italiyada bo'lganmisan?

Indicative mood of Uzbek language: Indicative refers to an action that can or cannot be clearly done in one of three times. Indicative indicates three times. For instance; Ikromjon went out into the street looking at the sky. (from works of S.A.)

In both languages the Indicative mood represents an action as a fact:

Here is here- U shu yerda

He said so- U shunday dedi

2. Imperative mood of English language: Verbs in the form of the imperative mood express the urge to perform an action: command, offer, request,

etc. The subject is absent in such sentences, and the predicate is used in the form of an infinitive without "to". Usually, an order, offer or request is addressed to a second person (you, you) or to a group of people, for example:

Give me my phone, please. Telefonimni olib berving.

Learn the lessons of life, because learning life is necessary! Hayot saboqlarini o'rgangin, chunki hayotni o'rganish zarur! (Omon Muxtor) [4.214p]

In order to express the prohibition to commit an action related to the 2nd person, the negation "don't (= do not)" is put before the verb in the form of the imperative mood
Don't make noise here! Bu yerda shovqin qilmang!

Don't to be late in lesson! Darsga kechikmang!

When calling for joint action, after the verb "let" the pronoun "us" (let us = let's) is used, which translates into Uzbek as "keling, qani ". When the speaker expresses his desire to perform the action himself, the pronoun "me" is used after the verb "let".

For instance:

Let us play volleyball! Qani, (Keling)voleybol oynaymiz!

Let me think one minute! O'ylab olishimga bir daqiqa bering!

In order to express the prohibition to perform an action, negation “don't (do not)” is placed before the service verb “let”:

Don't let him smoke here! Uning bu yerda chekishiga yo'l qo'ymang!

We use the imperative in requests and commands. Imperative statements have and understood subject of “you” and therefore take second-person verbs.

Sit down. (You sit down.)

Please take a number. (You please, take a number.)

Taking into consideration the meaning of the imperative mood, we can also refer to its field some interrogative sentences which actually express not a question, but request or a mild command. The predicate verb-form in such sentences coincides with the indicative mood in such cases. For example;

Will you open the door? -mild command.

Shall I do it now?

Modal verbs with an infinitive can be used in the imperative mood to express a request, a permission, a prohibition or an order. For example;

You may go now.

You must not stay here too.

You are to come at ten.

Imperative forms are formed by adding the following suffixes to verb bases in Uzbek language:

I Person	-y, -ay	O'qiy, boray	-ylik, -aylik	Boraylik
II Person	-gin, -gil	Borgin, borgil	-ing, -ingiz	Boring
III Person	-sin	borsin	-sinlar	borsinlar

In both languages the Imperative mood express the speaker's inducement (order, request, command, and the like) addressing to another person to do something;

Come here- Kelingiz

Wake up- Turingiz

3. Subjunctive mood. The subjunctive mood (istak mayli) donates actions that could occur in imaginary (unreal) situations.

In the Uzbek language, subjunctive mood sentences are formed structurally through the syntactic pattern [subjunctive mood – koshki]. In this case, the subjunctive mood symbol is a unit representing a subjunctive mood, and the koshki symbol represents a predicate form. Hence, as a result of the coming of the unit representing subjunctive mood in the function of the predicate, subjunctive mood sentences in a compact structure are formed. [6.128p] For instance;

I wish I were young again.

In Uzbek, istamoq – to desire, xohlamoq- to want, tusamoq – to passion verb lexemes are actively used to express desire. Also, the lexemes of istak, xohish, and ishtiyiq also directly reflect the desire of the subject when it comes to the function of the predicate in speech. For example: O'qishga kirish uning istagi bor (xohishi) edi. It can be used interchangeably with U o'qishga kirishni istardi, U o'qishga kirishni xohlardi, U o'qishga kirish ishtioqida edi sentences.

In sources, the -sa affix acts as a conditional affix as a means of connecting parts of a conditional sentence;

The suffix “-sa” is a conditional mood form of the verb.

I Person: If I write (Agar yozsam)

II Person: If you write (Agar yozsang)

III Person: If they write (Agar yozsalar)

It is noted that the conditional relation is further enhanced if the part of speech consisting of these affixed verbs contains conditional conjunctions such as agar,

mabodo, and basharti [3, p. 270]. But this is not a permanent situation. Although the part of a subjunctive mood sentence consists of verbs with the -sa affix, and conditional conjunctions such as agar, mabodo, and basharti are used in the sentence, conditional sentences may not be formed. [5.98p] For example:

Agar shu tuxumlarni yigirma kun bosib bersangiz, jahon faniga buyuk hissa qo'shgan bo'lardingiz. - If you pressed these eggs for twenty days, you would have made a great contribution to world science. (S. Ahmad. “Napoleon Mamajonov”) [3.174p]

The Uzbek language has these moods of the verb. Each verb mood has its own rules and affixes that give meaning to words when used in a sentences and depending on their function.

In conclusion, we would like to point out that modality is a notional category which expresses the relation of the utterance to reality. Both languages have verb tenses, moods of the verb and they have their own functions. In Uzbek language, there are four verb conjugations, each of which has its own suffix. In English language, there are mainly three verb moods, and they give meaning to sentences depending on their functions.

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